

Identification of Paramagnetic Centers in Irradiated F-Doped Silica by First-Principle Calculations

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Although fluorine is one of the most important dopants of silica, for several decades fluorine-related paramagnetic defects have been very elusive. Yet, a recent experimental investigation [L. Skuja et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 131, 256 903 (2023)] has claimed the identification of a new paramagnetic center, that is, the E'(F) center, responsible for a 10.5 mT hyperfine doublet in irradiated F-doped silica glass. Due to the lack of theoretical investigations, the reliability of the assignment proposed for the E'(F) has been under debate so far. In this work two alternative structural models, here labeled as the 2fSi-F and E'_F models, are investigated and discussed by means of first-principle calculations of electron paramagnetic resonance parameters, and further evidence in favor of the 2fSi-F model is provided. The latter consists of a threefold-coordinated Si atom, which is bonded to two bridging oxygen atoms and to one fluorine atom and that features an unpaired electron in an sp³ orbital. Furthermore, through first-principles nudged elastic band calculations it is shown that, under irradiation, generation mechanisms involving an interconversion between E'_γ and E'(F) centers can occur, with no need for precursors like the tetrahedral unit SiO₂F₂ or twofold Si centers.

1. Introduction

Fluorine-doped silica glass offers several remarkable advantages with respect to other kinds of silica glass. For instance it exhibits

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considerable transparency improvements with respect to high-OH silica for applications in the deep ultraviolet region.^[1,2] This is because fluorine-doping eliminates hydroxyl groups whose absorption is nonnegligible at ≈160 nm.^[3,4] Moreover doping silica with fluorine results in lowering the refraction index, making F-doped silica an excellent cladding material for optical fibers,^[5] in particular for the production of ultralow loss fibers.^[6,7] Last but not least, a light doping with fluorine improves the resistance of silica to radiation-induced damage, a critical property for optical fibers to be used in harsh environments, such as space communication or nuclear applications.^[8–10] Hence understanding the fluorine-related radiation induced point defects, as well as the mechanisms behind the fluorine action, is of paramount importance for further improvements of radiation-tolerant optical fibers.

F-doped silica under irradiation was the object of several past investigations in the field of optical fibers during the last three decades.^[11,12] For instance, Arai et al.^[12] found that F doping (for F concentration up to ≈2.5%) effectively removed ≡Si-Cl units without introducing oxygen deficient centers (ODCs) and/or ≡Si-H and also inferred that ≡Si-F units do not behave as a precursor of the E' center. Moreover, Arai et al.^[12] remarked that Si-F bond is stronger than Si-H and Si-Cl bonds. Quite surprisingly, despite electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) has been used for several decades to study radiation-induced point defects in F-doped silica only in recent years paramagnetic centers related to fluorine (¹⁹F isotope) were hypothesized^[13] and finally detected in a recent investigation.^[14]

Furthermore Skuja et al.^[14] suggests that starting from a diamagnetic precursor center like the tetrahedron O₂SiF₂, which was identified by NMR spectroscopy in fluorinated mesoporous silica,^[15] a paramagnetic center, named E'(F),^[14] could be generated under irradiation via the displacement or radiolysis of a F atom

where we explicitly indicate the presence of a bond with—and of the unpaired electron with a •. According to Skuja et al.^[14] the structure of the E'(F) center consists of a fluorine-modified Si dangling bond that is, a threefold-coordinated Si atom which is bonded to two bridging oxygen atoms and to one fluorine atom

and features an unpaired electron in an sp^3 orbital. The $E'(F)$ center is regarded^[14] as responsible for a 10.5 mT hyperfine doublet in irradiated F-doped silica glass (≈ 0.5 to 7 wt% F-doped), while exhibiting a g-tensor very close to the one known for the E'_γ center.^[14,16] Hence among the E' class of paramagnetic centers in silica the closest analogous to the $E'(F)$ is represented by the H(I) center, where a hydrogen atom is bound to a twofold Si atom and where the hyperfine interaction between the unpaired electron and the hydrogen nucleus originates a 7.4 mT doublet.^[17–19] However, we note that the generation mechanism given in Equation (1) might be not so efficient since the probability of breaking a Si–F bond is likely to be low because of its high bonding strength, and moreover, the resulting atomic F may not travel long distances because of its high reactivity within the silica network. Hence, it is interesting to consider all other possible generation mechanisms besides the one of Equation (1).

In Awazu et al.^[20] the simultaneous generation of the 7.6 eV optical absorption band and of the 4.3 eV band (attributed to F_2 molecule) in fluorine doped silica glass under annealing (1000 °C) has led the authors to propose a thermal reaction

which may suggest that the interaction of fluorine with neutral oxygen vacancies under irradiation conditions may also lead, to some extent, to the formation of paramagnetic centers involving fluorine atoms. In fact, the Equation (2) suggests that in F-doped silica glass, under γ -irradiation/out-of-equilibrium processes that may imply also a charge transfer, one might observe a radiolytic process like

Moreover, under conditions that allow the diffusion of fluorine atoms^[20] one might observe a process like

In other words one could expect to observe a paramagnetic center

hereafter referred to as the E'_F center that might result from the interaction (Equation (4)) of a neutral oxygen vacancy and a fluorine atom,^[21] analogously to the trapping of atomic hydrogen at an oxygen vacancy site.^[22,23]

The present work by means of state-of-the-art first-principle calculations addresses the main issues related to the identification of the $E'(F)$ center, for which other models are here considered besides the one^[14] that may be generated through the process outlined in Equation (1). First, by exploiting available structures of the twofold Si center in silica,^[24] and also by generating new ones, we directly evaluate the EPR parameters for a wide set of configurations representative of Skuja's model of the $E'(F)$, i.e., for the 2fSi-F, which is a structural analog of the H(I) center.^[14] Next, we also consider an alternative model for the $E'(F)$ consisting in an E' center which features a fluorine atom among its next nearest neighbors (i.e., an E'_F) and that results

from the replacement of a bridging O atom with an F atom in our silica structures. Our EPR calculations provide support to the Skuja's model of the $E'(F)$, although we remark that the E'_F model also shows EPR parameters quite close to the experimental data and therefore might be a possible reason of the signal broadenings. Furthermore, by means of nudged elastic band (NEB) calculations, we show that 2fSi-F configurations could be generated, under irradiation conditions, if an E'_γ center is sufficiently close to $a \equiv \text{Si}-\text{F}$ group by overcoming an energy barrier of ≈ 1.5 eV. Since both the E' centers and the ODCs^[24] are universally formed, under irradiation, in any type of silica glass, the conversion path between E'_γ and 2fSi-F configurations constitutes an alternative mechanism to Equation (1) that could also explain the proportionality of $E'(F)$ generation to the concentration of Si–F group remarked in.^[14]

2. Results

2.1. 2fSi-F that is, the Skuja's Model of the $E'(F)$ Centers

By placing a F atom nearby the twofold Si defect in our silica structures (see Section 4) and by subsequently optimizing the atomic structure via a first-principle relaxation, we could generate about thirty paramagnetic centers, hereafter called 2fSi-F, which according to Skuja et al.^[14] represents the structural model of the $E'(F)$ center. In other words, the first-principles relaxation of 2fSi-F indicate that the twofold Si is a precursor of the Skuja's $E'(F)$ which, provided an F atom diffuses nearby a twofold Si (i.e., $\equiv\text{Si}$), might be generated via the following mechanism

Although in real samples the probability of the reaction between the twofold Si and the atomic F may be low because in fact it requires that atomic F has to form near a divalent Si, we note that for the present work the Equation (6) provides an efficient heuristic way to generate 2fSi-F structures. In **Figure 1** we show a ball-and-stick model together with the spin density of a 2fSi-F that is, an $E'(F)$ center according to Skuja's model.^[14] On average the Si–F bond in our calculations is ≈ 1.62 Å long with a standard deviation of 0.01 Å. The O–Si–O angle on average is 111.3° (std of 6.0°) while the O–Si–F angle is 106.1° (std of 4.2°) consistent with sp^3 hybridization as occurs in H(I) center and E' centers in silica.^[18]

In **Table 1** we give the calculated average of $A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ over all the models, 10.7 mT that agrees within one std (2.4 mT) with the 10.5 mT reported in Skuja et al.^[14] for the $E'(F)$ center. Moreover, the magnitude, 3.4 mT, of the anisotropic hyperfine coupling estimated by Skuja et al.^[14] is also quite close to the calculated average dipolar coupling in our models that is, $A_{\text{aniso}}(^{19}\text{F}) = 3.7$ mT together with a std of 0.6 mT. The latter anisotropic hyperfine coupling is fairly close to the one, 4.65 mT, we calculate for fluorine atoms of the SiF_3 radical (Table S1 and Figure S1, Supporting Information), in good agreement with the experimental reported value of ≈ 4.5 mT.^[25] The latter value is also close to the one, 4.4 mT, we calculate for a small cluster model of a 2fSi-F center (Table S1, Supporting Information), which suggests $E'(F)$ may show a larger anisotropic hfc in porous F-doped silica.

Figure 1. Ball-and-stick model and spin density (shaded) of a 2fSi-F configuration in model III representing an $E'(F)$ center according to Skuja's model^[14] (shown in the inset). O atoms (red), Si atoms (light brown) and F atom (light green) are shown.

The g -tensors found for the F-doped sample A and pure sample L in the experiment,^[14] are very close and both belong to the E'_γ class. Similarly the results of g -values calculated for the 2fSi-F in our silica models are all very close to those obtained for E'_γ , that is, to the E' puckered configurations,^[26] with minor differences of about a few hundreds ppm, noticeable in particular for the g_1 value. In Table 1 we also report the relative differences $g_{13} = g_1 - g_3$ and $g_{12} = g_1 - g_2$ which are converged within a few hundreds ppm for the presently used silica models^[27,28] (see also Figure S2, Supporting Information), and have revealed to be useful quantities for the assignments of paramagnetic defects.^[28,29] By comparing the g -values recorded for samples A and L^[14] we note that in the fluorinated sample A the g -tensor is slightly more orthorhombic (i.e., $g_{13} > g_{23}$) as compared to the pure sample L and that this trend is also confirmed by our ab-initio calculations. In fact, as compared to the g -values we previously calculated for the E'_γ ,^[26] the g -values here calculated for the 2fSi-F are slightly more orthorhombic, as can be noted by the increase (200 ppm) in

the g_{13} parameter, and by the decrease (130 ppm) in the g_{23} parameter (Table 1).

The calculations given in Table 1 indicate an average difference of ≈ 4.9 mT between the $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$ we found in 2fSi-F centers and the one we previously calculated for E'_γ centers,^[26] which is considerably larger than 2.4 mT we infer from the values estimated (44.4–42.0) in Skuja et al.^[14] We note that a trend exists between the $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$ and the Si-F distance so that longer Si-F distances correspond to larger isotropic hfcs on the threefold-coordinated Si atom (Figure 2). The number of 2fSi-F configurations collected in our models might be not enough to sample correctly the Si-F bond length distribution, in particular with a likely overestimation of the Si-F distance and thus leading to an overestimate of the average $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$. In contrast, the value 44.4 mT^[14] is obtained through a fitting procedure of a difference spectrum which may also be affected by some systematic error.

2.2. The E'_F and $E'_{\beta F}$ Configurations

The fluorine trapped center resulting from Equation (3) could be further distinguished in two kinds. A first one where the “umbrella” of the three-fold silicon is oriented toward the fluorine atom as in Equation (4), and a second one where the umbrella is backpuckered, that is, oriented away from the fluorine atom

which is the fluorine analogous of the E'_β center model proposed by Griscom,^[23] resulting from the hydrogen trapping at an oxygen vacancy site and corresponding to the E'_2 center in quartz.^[30] Hence, we hereafter refer to Equation (7) as to an $E'_{\beta F}$ center.

In order to generate possible alternative configurations of the $E'(F)$ center, we then considered the case of a fluorine atom that interacts with a neutral oxygen vacancy as in Equation (3) and (4). Paramagnetic centers as expressed by Equation (5) were obtained by replacing an oxygen atom (for each oxygen site in the silica model) with fluorine atom and then by performing a first-principle relaxation of the structure. The relaxation of these configurations has led, for the $\approx 13\%$ of cases, to an $E'_{\beta F}$ configuration (Figure 3c) where a backward puckered E'_γ center has formed, and the F atom has bound to the other threefold Si atom, so that almost no spin-density is found on the F atom as indicated by the small value of the ^{19}F isotropic hfc (Table 2). Moreover, the

Table 1. Calculated average g -values and isotropic hfcs $A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ and $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$ (absolute values in mT) of the 2fSi-F center in our vitreous SiO_2 models in this work (TW) compared to experimental data of F-doped sample A featuring the $E'(F)$ center.^[14] For comparison with the E'_γ center, we also report the g -values and the isotropic hfc on the silicon atom as obtained in experiment,^[16] and from ab-initio calculations for the puckered configurations.^[26] Standard deviations are given in parenthesis. ($g_{12} = g_1 - g_2$ and $g_{13} = g_1 - g_3$ are in ppm).

Models	Refs	g_1	g_2	g_3	g_{12}	g_{13}	$A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$	$A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$
2fSi-F	TW ^{a)}	2.00177(12)	2.00059(30)	1.99988(24)	1180	1890	10.7(2.4)	46.0(3.8)
Puckered	[26]	2.00186(09)	2.00055(18)	2.00017(16)	1310	1690	–	41.1(2.6)
Sample A	[14]	2.00175	2.00065	2.00026	1100	1490	10.5	44.4
E'_γ	[16]	2.00175	2.00056	2.00030	1190	1450	–	42

^{a)}the average of g values has been obtained by excluding the smallest size (71 atom) silica models.

Figure 2. a) Isotropic part $A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ and b) anisotropic part $A_{\text{aniso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ of the hyperfine tensor on fluorine atom, and c) variation of the isotropic hfc on silicon atom [$\delta A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$] with respect to puckered^[26] E'_F configurations (41.1 mT), plotted versus Si–F bond length in 2fSi–F configurations. Data of 2fSi–F generated in model I (black square), model II (red square) and model III (green squares) are shown and also as obtained from the 2fSi models of Ref. [42] with 71 atom (blue discs) and 191 atom (blue squares) cells. Experimental data are shown with red horizontal lines.

g-tensor and the isotropic hfc $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$ of $E'_{\beta\text{F}}$ centers are practically equivalent to those of the E'_F , as well represented by the puckered configurations in model III (Table 2).

In the remaining 87% of the relaxations, we obtained an E'_F center facing a $\text{SiO}_3 + \text{F}$ tetrahedron, as shown in Figure 3a,b, that is here referred to as an E'_F configuration. In the E'_F a non-negligible spin-density is found on the F atom, the amount of which depends on the local geometry, in particular from the distance between the threefold silicon atom carrying the unpaired spin and the fluorine atom (Figure 4a). The average Si–F bond length in E'_F configurations is about 1.60 Å with a std of 0.01 Å, about 0.02 Å shorter than found in 2fSi–F configurations. As far as concerns the $\text{Si}^{\text{DB}}\text{–F}$ distance of E'_F configurations, that is, the distance between the fluorine atom and the silicon with a dangling bond (Si^{DB}), we register on average a value of ≈ 2.7 Å with a rather broad distribution (std ≈ 0.2 Å) in all our silica models.

Figure 3. a) Ball-and-stick model and spin density (shaded) of an E'_F center. O atoms (red), Si atoms (light brown) and F atom (light green) are shown. b) A simplified sketch of the E'_F defect structure. c) A sketch of an $E'_{\beta\text{F}}$ configuration with a backward puckered Si, analogous to an E'_{β} ,^[23] where spin-density on F is negligible.

The E'_F configurations show a g-tensor (Table 2) almost indistinguishable from the one calculated for the 2fSi–F configurations, that is, for the Skuja's model (Table 1). Yet, the g-values suggest a slightly more axial center than calculated for the 2fSi–F (i.e., a g_{23} closer to g_{13}) in particular with a $g_{23} \approx 0.00130$ larger than the experimental data for the fluorinated A (0.00110) and closer to the value given for the pure sample L (0.00132).^[14] A higher axiality of the E'_F with respect to the 2fSi–F configurations is understandable since the Si of the former center

Table 2. Calculated average g-values and isotropic hfcs (absolute values in mT) of E'_F (Figure 3b) and $E'_{\beta F}$ (Figure 3c) and E'_γ (puckered) configurations in our model III of silica (103, 18, and 101 configurations, respectively) in this work (TW) compared to experimental data of sample A^[14] featuring the $E'(F)$ center, and of E'_γ centers in amorphous silica.^[16] standard deviations are given in parenthesis. ($g_{12} = g_1 - g_2$ and $g_{13} = g_1 - g_3$ in ppm). For sake of readability data for models I and II are included in table S3, supporting information.

Models	Refs.	g_1	g_2	g_3	g_{12}	g_{13}	$A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$	$A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$
E'_F	TW	2.00162(09)	2.00032(25)	1.99974(29)	1300	1880	12.5(4.9)	45.7(3.3)
$E'_{\beta F}$	TW	2.00169(11)	2.00055(30)	1.99988(28)	1140	1810	0.5(0.1)	42.4(4.4)
Puckered	TW	2.00168(09)	2.00044(24)	2.00000(24)	1246	1682	–	41.7(3.9)
Sample A	[14]	2.00175	2.00065	2.00026	1100	1490	10.5	44.4
E'_γ	[16]	2.00175	2.00056	2.00030	1190	1450	–	42

Figure 4. Trends between a) the isotropic part of the hyperfine tensor $A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ on fluorine atom, b) the anisotropic part $A_{\text{aniso}}(^{19}\text{F})$, and c) variation of the isotropic hfc [$\delta A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$] on the silicon atom as referred to the puckered E'_γ ^[26] versus the $\text{Si}^{\text{DB}}\text{-F}$ distance, as calculated in our E'_F configurations. Data from model I (black square), model II (blue circles) and model III (green squares) are shown. Averages over the models and experimental data are shown with (red/dotted) horizontal lines.

features three equivalent Si–O bonds, while in the 2fSi–F the local symmetry of the center is lowered since the Si here features a Si–F bond and two equivalent Si–O bonds.

The average isotropic hfc on the fluorine atom $A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ is ≈ 12.5 mT, rather close to the one calculated for the 2fSi–F configurations (within one std). Yet, the hfc shows a quite large spread (≈ 5 mT), about double of the average we calculated in our models for the 2fSi–F configurations, and considerably larger than the full width at half maximum (≈ 1.5 mT) used by

Skuja et al.^[14] to simulate the experimental spectrum. As for the $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$, the calculated average (45.7 mT) is rather close (within one std) to the ones calculated for the 2fSi–F configurations and is about 5 mT larger than the $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$ calculated for the E'_γ puckered configurations.^[26] The latter increase, although larger in magnitude, may underlie the observed experimental increase in the fluorinated sample given in Skuja et al.^[14] Both the isotropic hfc $A_{\text{iso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ and anisotropic constant $A_{\text{aniso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ in Figure 4 show a decreasing trend versus $\text{Si}^{\text{DB}}\text{-F}$ distance. Yet, as one can notice in Figure 2b and 4b, the dipolar part of the hyperfine tensor for E'_F configurations (average over all models $A_{\text{aniso}} \approx 1.9$ mT, with std of 0.8 mT) is markedly different with respect to the one calculated for 2fSi–F configurations ($A_{\text{aniso}} = 3.65$ mT) and as estimated ($A_{\text{aniso}} = 3.4$ mT) by Skuja et al.^[14] which indicates a substantial difference of the spin-density shape at the F nucleus in 2fSi–F with respect to the one of E'_F configurations (Figure 3a). Hence, the previous remark and the data of Table 2 suggest that, although the E'_F model could possibly contribute to the broadening of the EPR spectrum of the $E'(F)$ center, it can not be considered as the first option for its explanation, while the most safe attribution is still represented by the Skuja's model (i.e., the 2fSi–F configurations).

2.3. Paramagnetic Defect Interconversions

In this section we discuss the possible interconversion between E' centers and the 2fSi–F or E'_F configurations. The Skuja's $E'(F)$ model, that is, the 2fSi–F model, could undergo a conversion mechanism, through ionization and subsequent neutralization as shown in Figure 5. A 2fSi–F in model I was relaxed in the positive charge state that is, by removing one electron from the system. The relaxed structure, shown in the center of Figure 5, features a threefold-coordinated oxygen atom that is formed as result of a bonding process between the threefold Si atom of the 2fSi–F and a nearby oxygen atom of the silica network. By further relaxing the structure again in the neutral charge state (i.e., by adding back one electron) we see that a Si–O bond of the threefold oxygen atom is broken, which can lead to the formation of a standard E'_γ center that is, an unpaired electron on a sp^3 orbital of a silicon atom threefold-coordinated with oxygen atoms. Alternatively the system relaxes back to the 2fSi–F configuration. In other words, an $E' + \text{SiO}_3\text{F}$ complex can be obtained by means of a charging procedure, as shown

Figure 5. (left) A 2fSi-F configuration (i.e., an $E'(F)$ center) might be ionized and form a complex involving a threefold O atom and a SiO_3F tetrahedron (center), which can then be neutralized and transform into an $E'_\gamma + \text{SiO}_3\text{F}$ complex (right). Silicon, oxygen, fluorine atoms are represented with pink, red and green balls. The unpaired electron is shown with a blue dot.

Table 3. Number of analyzed energy paths N and average energy barriers (eV) between 2fSi-F and E'_γ configurations (E_{\pm}^b) and vice-versa (E_{\pm}^b), in silica models I and II as calculated by using the NEB method (see Figure 5). For comparison it is also reported the energy barrier between E'_F and $E'_{\beta F}$ configurations (see Figure 3c,b). $\Delta E = E_{\pm}^b - E_{\pm}^b$ is the energy difference between the two minima. Errors on images are less than 0.1 eV. Standard deviations are given in parenthesis.

	N	E_{\pm}^b	E_{\pm}^b	ΔE (eV)
2fSi-F $\rightleftharpoons E'_\gamma$	14	0.9(0.2)	1.5(0.4)	0.6
$E'_F \rightleftharpoons E'_{\beta F}$	3 ^{a)}	1.1(0.1)	1.2(0.2)	0.1

^{a)}The distance $\text{Si}^{\text{DB}}\text{-F}$ in the E'_F varies from 2.47 Å to 3.10 Å.

in Figure 5, and since the F atom is rather far from the Si dangling bond, the latter well represents the usual E'_γ center.^[26] The final $E'_\gamma + \text{SiO}_3\text{F}$ configuration is usually lower in energy by ≈ 0.6 eV with respect to the initial 2fSi-F center (Table 3). Such a large energy difference suggests that a preferential conversion of 2fSi-F configurations toward E'_γ -like centers could occur during prolonged irradiation or sample annealing.

In fact, even when the sample is not irradiated, the interconversion of the defects can occur although not through ionization as explained here above. Actually the interconversion is still possible if the system has enough (kinetic) energy to overcome a thermal barrier. By means of NEB calculations, we calculate the energy barriers for the conversion from 2fSi-F to E'_γ and vice-versa (Figure 6). Energy barriers are on average about ≈ 1 eV, which suggests that the direct conversion of 2fSi-F to E'_γ is a quite unlikely process (at room temperature). We note that the transition state as found by the NEB calculation closely resembles the ionized (positively charged) configuration of Figure 5.

Also for the E'_F we calculate an energy barrier of about ≈ 1 eV to convert to an $E'_{\beta F}$, consistently with results previously found for the Si-Si to SiFO interconversion through PM mechanism.^[24] Moreover, past investigations similarly found a rather large barrier of 0.6 eV for the interconversion path between E'_2 and E'_4 centers in α -quartz.^[30] The final $E'_{\beta F}$ configurations is slightly lower in energy (on average ≈ 0.1 eV) with respect to the initial E'_F configuration, which again suggests that no preferential conversion toward $E'_{\beta F}$ centers should occur during irradiation or sample annealing.

Figure 6. Example of NEB energy path for the interconversion between a 2fSi-F and an E'_γ configuration in model I.

In summary, the present NEB calculations suggest that, during the irradiation process of the sample, the 2fSi-F centers could interconvert to E'_γ centers. Yet, once the irradiation is stopped the 2fSi-F can not convert anymore to E'_γ at room temperature due to the large energy barrier that occurs between the two minima, and so it can not be bleached simply as a consequence of an ageing process. Incidentally, we note that Figure 6 may represent a generation path of 2fSi-F centers, that is, of $E'(F)$ centers, that does not require the precursor presence of twofold Si atoms, but rather the occurrence of a close enough pair of a three-fold Si atom and a SiO_3F tetrahedron.

3. Conclusions

We have investigated, by means of first-principle calculations of EPR parameters, two alternative models of fluorine-related paramagnetic centers, i.e., the 2fSi-F and E'_F configurations, that could explain the recently observed $E'(F)$ center in silica.

Although both models, the 2fSi-F and the E'_F centers, provide a fair agreement with experimental data for the isotropic hfcs at ^{19}F and ^{29}Si nuclei, as well as for the g principal values, there are some important differences. The first one concerns the anisotropic part of the hyperfine tensor $A_{\text{aniso}}(^{19}\text{F})$ that is quite different, by a factor of two, in 2fSi-F configurations with respect to the one calculated for the E'_F . Yet, only the value calculated for the 2fSi-F configurations is evidently consistent with the one reported by Skuja et al.^[14] thus providing support to the interpretation of the $E'(F)$ center in terms of the 2fSi-F configurations. A second difference is found by analyzing the calculated g -values: the g -tensor of E'_F seems to be slightly more axial than found for the 2fSi-F (≈ 200 ppm difference in g_{23}), consistently with the lower local symmetry (within the nearest neighbors shell) of the latter center. These differences however, are quite small to allow for a straightforward identification of the $E'(F)$ center on the basis of the sole g -tensor, which may require an improvement of the accuracy both for the experimental and calculated g -values.

Finally, by means of NEB calculations, we have investigated an interconversion path between 2fSi-F and E'_γ -like configurations, which may represent an alternative generation mechanism of the

$E'(F)$ center that do not require the precursory presence of twofold Si atoms or of SiO_2F_2 tetrahedra in the irradiated silica sample.

4. Methodology

The calculations carried out in this work are based on density functional theory (DFT). The Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional has been adopted.^[31] Norm-conserving Trouiller-Martins pseudopotentials with gauge, including projector augmented wave (GIPAW) reconstruction are used^[26,32] and the Kohn-Sham wavefunctions are expanded in a basis of plane waves up to a cutoff energy of 80 Ry.^[33] The wavefunctions were expanded at the Γ point of the Brillouin zone, as justified by the typical size of the simulation cell (hundreds atoms) and the large band gap in silica based glassy systems.^[34–36] Geometry optimizations and EPR parameters have been obtained by means of spin-polarized calculations as implemented in the Quantum-Espresso (QE) package.^[37,38] Each atomic configuration was relaxed using the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno algorithm^[37] and a force threshold of $\approx 10^{-3}$ Ryd/Å (or lower). The EPR parameters are calculated by exploiting the GIPAW method as available in the QE package.^[33,37,38]

In this work we adopt three F-doped silica supercells containing 108 atoms, 144, and 192 atoms at the experimental density (2.2 g cm^{-3}) and are hereafter referred to as model I and model II, and III respectively. The original silica model I and model II were previously employed to investigate silicon ODCs (SiODC) in vitreous silica ($\nu\text{-SiO}_2$)^[24,26,39] and later used in^[28] for the discussion of Ge paramagnetic centers in Ge-doped silica. Model III was generated in Martin-Samos et al.^[40] and used in a recent study of Sn-doped silica.^[29] By adopting three amorphous silica models we can considerably increase the number (statistics) of twofold silicon defects with respect to those previously analyzed in the literature.^[24,28] As far as we know there is not straightforward method to generate twofold coordinated silicon defects in silica in a periodic supercell silica with no other coordination defect.^[24,41] In particular, the method previously described^[24,39] requires a series of subsequent calculations, and therefore it might become time consuming for large silica models. In order to increase the statistics of twofold Si atoms we also considered ten silica structures containing a twofold Si center that were generated by Anderson et al.^[42] in models with size ranging from 71 to 191 atoms. Hence, for the 2fSi–F centers (Section 2.1), we could also analyze the supercell size effect on the EPR parameters, which are discussed in the Supporting Information, Table S2, Supporting Information, (similar analysis has also been done for the E'_F centers in Table S3, Supporting Information), and establish that it has no relevant impact on the conclusions of the present work.

Fluorine in nature is found in a stable isotope (^{19}F), that carries a 1/2 nuclear spin, with 100% natural abundance and with a nuclear g-factor (g_N) of 5.257736.^[43,44] Silicon has three naturally occurring stable isotopes ^{28}Si , ^{29}Si , ^{30}Si , of which only ^{29}Si (natural abundance 4.7%) carries a nonzero (1/2) nuclear spin, with a nuclear g-factor of -1.11058 .^[43,44] The hyperfine spin-Hamiltonian

$$H_{\text{hf}} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{I} \quad (8)$$

arises from the coupling between the electron spin \mathbf{S} and the nuclear spin \mathbf{I} through the hyperfine tensor \mathbf{A} which can be decomposed into an isotropic part A_{iso} , that is, the isotropic hyperfine coupling (hfc), and a traceless anisotropic tensor \mathbf{B}

$$A_{ij} = A_{\text{iso}}\delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \quad (9)$$

The isotropic hfc is related to the spin-density at the site \mathbf{R} of the nucleus: $A_{\text{iso}} = \frac{8\pi}{3} g_e \beta_e g_N \beta_N n_s(\mathbf{R})$. The anisotropic tensor \mathbf{B} results from the dipolar interaction, that can be written for a spin 1/2 center as

$$B_{ij} = g_N \beta_N g_e \beta_e \int \left(\frac{3r_i r_j}{r^5} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{r^3} \right) n_s(\mathbf{r}) dV \quad (10)$$

where $n_s(\mathbf{r}) = n_{\uparrow}(\mathbf{r}) - n_{\downarrow}(\mathbf{r})$ is the electron spin density, g_N and g_e are the nuclear gyromagnetic ratio and the free-electron g-factor, β_N and β_e are the nuclear and Bohr magnetons.^[45] In its principal axes the tensor B can be described using its principal values B_1 , B_2 , B_3 . If an axial (or quasi-axial) symmetry is present (assume it along direction 3) then one can further distinguish among the parallel ($B_3 = B_{\parallel}$) and orthogonal components ($B_{\perp} = B_1 = B_2$, where $B_{\parallel} + 2B_{\perp} = 0$). In the following we use A_{aniso} to refer to the $|B_{\perp}|$ component of the anisotropic tensor \mathbf{B} .

Isotropic hyperfine couplings were calculated using the GIPAW method with core polarization effects as implemented (Slater X) in the QE-GIPAW module of QE package.^[46] For light elements, for example, C, pseudopotentials based calculations of hyperfine couplings can be computed with an accuracy comparable to that of all electron calculations, provided the effect of core polarization is included.^[45,46]

For the calculation of the reaction pathways, energy barriers, transition states along the minimum energy path (MEP) we adopt the climbing image NEB method as implemented in QE.^[37] For each application of the NEB method we used ten configurations (NEB images). A threshold of 0.1 eV \AA^{-1} (on the norm of the force orthogonal to the path) was applied as criterion for the convergence of the MEP.

The present study relies on a standard generalized gradient approximation (GGA) functional, the PBE functional, that suffers from the self-interaction error. This drawback may lead to inaccuracies in describing localized electronic states, such as self-trapped electrons and holes in insulating materials, as it is the case, for example, for self-trapped holes in pure silica, in Al-doped quartz and for the electron polaron in titania.^[47–49] However, as it is apparent from the past literature,^[26,50–52] the nature of the E' centers in silica make the usage of beyond-standard DFT methods not so relevant, and calculated EPR parameters, already at GGA level, are exceptionally good when compared to experimental data, as it has been shown in many studies.^[26,28,52] In contrast, previous hybrid functional (B3LYP)-based calculations of EPR parameters for E' centers were carried out using small cluster models,^[50,51] and hence suffered of the lack of long-range effects. Despite this drawback and despite their limited number of configurations, the B3LYP results reported in^[50,51,53,54] for the EPR parameters of E'_γ -like configurations are in fair agreement (e.g., $A_{\text{iso}}(^{29}\text{Si})$ is within

one std) with our previous DFT-based calculations for puckered configurations.^[26] Moreover, we here provide further evidence of the reliability of the present DFT-based calculations through benchmark calculations at Γ point carried out for the E'_1 center in α -quartz using large supercells (up to $4 \times 4 \times 4$ supercell i.e., a size of 576 atoms) for which the calculated g_r values show an excellent agreement with experimental data,^[55,56] within only ≈ 200 ppm (see Figure S2, Supporting Information). We also carried out test calculations for a small cluster model of the 2fSi-F center [i.e., the $(F_3Si-O)_2-Si-F^*$ atomic cluster] using B3LYP functional as implemented in the ORCA code,^[57] and found only minor variations (e.g., isotropic hfc varies up to ≈ 0.5 mT) with respect to calculations done, as explained here above, by using QE-GIPAW code (Table S1, Supporting Information) and which do not affect the conclusions of the present work.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

density functional theory, E' center, $E'(F)$, electron paramagnetic resonance, silica

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